

EVALUATION OF SOME TOBACCO GENETIC RESOURCES STORED IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

Evaluation of genetic resources plays an important role in crossbreeding and seed production. In 2023, the Vietnam Tobacco Institute tested 24 tobacco genetic resources belonging to Flue-cured, Burley, and Dark and Cigar tobacco groups. The objective was to evaluate some morphological characteristics of rejuvenated tobacco gene resources and determine the correlation between some morphological characteristics of flowers and seed yield. The experiment was setted according to the sequential method by variety. Experimental results showed that Dark and Cigar tobacco varieties had the highest biological height (171 - 172.4 cm), then Flue-cured tobaccos (164.9 cm), and the lowest was Burley tobacco varieties. Tobacco varieties had leaf numbers from 17.7 - 20.2 leaves/plant, the most leaf numbers belonged to the Flue-cured and Burley tobacco varieties (20.2 leaves/plant), and a number of the fewest leaves belonged to the Cigar variety (17.7 leaves/plant). The Flue-cured tobacco varieties had the biggest leaf length, but a narrow width, 58.4 cm and 21.6 cm, respectively; the short leaf length was Cigar tobaccos (53.1 cm), but the width of leaf was large, with 27.3 cm. The weight of 1000 seeds and the germination rate of the genetic resources achieved the quality requirements. Inflorescence distribution, flower length, number of capsules/plant and off flower time affected 78.5% of seed yield. Seed yield positively correlated with the number of capsules/plant and mature time, but negatively correlated with flower length and inflorescence distribution. Experimental results are important information for crossbreeding, seed production, and selection of beneficial genotypes for production and research.

Keywords: Tobacco Genetic Resources, Tobacco Seed, Regeneration Of Germplasm, SPSS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L.) is a short industrial crop with high economic value (Moon et al., 2009), belongs to the *Solanaceae* family and has many different species (Ren, Timko, 2001). Dried tobacco leaves are used in other products, such as cigarettes, cigars, etc., and green leaves are extracted into food proteins. Characteristic of tobacco plants with nicotine alkaloid, nornicotine and anabasine. Nicotine is a material for producing pesticides and many other chemical products (Kovtunyk et al., 2001).

Tobacco genetic resources provide crossbreeding with yield and quality goals (Z. Porkabiri et al., 2018). Success in creating new tobacco varieties depends on the availability of genetic resources (Khomutova et al., 2015) and genetic information (yield, quality, disease resistance and tolerance to environmental conditions). This information is recorded during the evaluation, propagation, and regeneration of genetic resources, which is necessary information for tobacco seed production to ensure yield and quality (Savina et al., 2017, Andrade et al., 2018).

The formation of tobacco seed yield is a complex process, influenced by many factors, such as environmental conditions, climate, soil, and development of reproductive organs, growing time and morphological characteristics of different tobacco types (Savina et al., 2007). Proactive production of seed yield with quality plays an important role in production of tobacco seeds and tobacco materials. According to the study of Lázaro A et al., 2019 on rice, seed yield depends on weather and climate conditions, the plant's growth and the genetic resources. Based on the morphology establishment time of plants, leaf surface area, number of leaves, the total number of branches, a good number of branches, etc can help seed producers have the right impact to increase seed yield. In research on beans, harvest index and biological yield are the main selection criteria to improve grain yield. In addition, genotype characteristics with long/short mature time also affect seed yield (ALBAYRAK et al., 2006). Z. Porkabiri et al., 2018, using eight morphological traits, such as plant height, leaf length, leaf width, number of leaves per plant, stem diameter, leaf area, dry leaf yield and fresh leaf yield to evaluate 25 tobacco genetic resources to determine yield, the results show that there is a positive relationship between leaf length, dry yield, fresh yield and leaf area, while there is no relationship between leaf length and stem diameter. To breed new high yield varieties is necessary to base on the characteristics of leaf length, width and leaf area (Z. Porkabiri et al., 2018). In crossbreeding, tobacco genetic diversity plays an important role. Natural genetic diversity is being deployed on many crops to detect desirable genes in production. Studying tobacco genetic diversity is very significant in breeding, some characteristics as morphological (Wenping et al., 2009; Zeba and Isbat, 2011) and chemical (Darvishzadeh et al., 2011). 2011) has been exploited and used.

In Vietnam, tobacco is also a short industrial crop, with high economic value, popularly grown in Cao Bang, Bac Kan, Lang Son, Gia Lai and Tay Ninh provinces, with an area of about 5.500 hectares (Nguyen Van Chin et al., 2023). Tobacco is a hunger eradication and poverty alleviation crop for tobacco growing farmers. Many popular tobacco varieties in Vietnam, such as GL7, GL9, and D65, with high yield, good quality and diseased resistance are bred from genetic resources kept at the Vietnam Tobacco Institute. By

2023, the Vietnam Tobacco Institute is storing 217 tobacco genetic resources belonging to the group of Flue cured, Dark, Burley, Cigar, Oriental, Semi-oriental and Wild tobaccos. Seeds that were stored for a long time will lose their germinable ability. To prevent the loss of valuable genetic resources, Genebanks may regenerate those genetic resources with good quantity, and quality for the maintenance of those seeds for further conservation. During the maintenance of germplasm tobaccos, have to check the vitality of the seeds to ensure genetic diversity. To check for a decline in genetic resources, seeds should be periodically tested through time by the method of a germination test (FAO 2014). During storage, genetic resources with a germination rate of less than 70% or a small seed amount of fewer than 5 grams should be multiplied, evaluated for growth and development factors, and taken seeds and stored. In recent years, evaluating the morphological traits and weather conditions on seed yield has not been studied much. In this study, we mainly evaluated some mainly morphological characteristics of rejuvenated tobacco gene sources and initially determined the correlation between some morphological traits of flowers and tobacco seed yield.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted in the Tobacco Institute's Branch in Ba Vi District, Hanoi city, where carried out the tobacco experiments, from December 2022 to May 2023. Average temperature, rainfall and sunshine hours increased gradually from planting to harvesting periods. The weather of planting time, in February with a temperature of 20°C, rainfall: 14 mm and hours of sunshine: 13 hours; and coming in May, respectively are 28.5°C, 88 mm and 172 hours.

Twenty-four tobacco varieties (Table 1) were sown in disease-free nurseries. When the seedlings had 2 - 3 leaves were transplanted into pots and planted in the experimental field when the seedlings had 4 - 6 leaves. The experiment was planted sequentially by plots, each plot for a variety. The size of each plot was 15 x 3.6 m in length and width, without repetition (according to FAO 2014, Standards for regeneration section). The distance between plant and plant was 0.6 m, and row and row was 1.2 m. The fertilizer rate of the experiment was 90N:180P₂O₅: 270 K₂O, with N: NH₄NO₃, P: Ca (H₂PO₄)₂ and K: K₂SO₄, and the basic fertilizing rate of 100% P₂O₅, 1/3 N and 1/3 K at the planting stage, and a total of the remaining amount of N and K at 30 days after planting.

Table 1: Twenty-four tobacco genetic resources for study

Variety	Tobacco type	Variety	Tobacco type	Variety	Tobacco type
Cocker 411	Flue-curing	VTL 81	Flue-curing	Philip 2	Dark
Cu 263	Flue-curing	Tennessee 90	Burley	RMB 34	Dark
RG 17	Flue-curing	Banket A1	Burley	Thang Lay	Dark
Speight 168	Flue-curing	Va 528	Burley	Quảng Nam	Dark
TBE 2	Flue-curing	Kentucky 14	Burley	Lào Cai 1	Dark
TV 28	Flue-curing	Riogrand	Dark	D2	Cigar
TV 30	Flue-curing	NL Madole	Dark	Criocdo	Cigar
VT 21	Flue-curing	Philip 1	Dark	Havana	Cigar

The bunch of capsules were harvested when 2/3 of the capsules turn brown, and kept separately in storage for 25 - 30 days. Tobacco seeds were dehumidified to 7.5%. Monitor agri-biological characteristics according to the guidelines of UPOV, 2002 and the guidelines for the experimental implementation of the Vietnam Tobacco Institute, 2012. Mainly monitoring indicators: High biological plant, the total number of leaves, width and height of inflorescence, flower length, number of capsules/plant, time from planting to flowering and harvesting, position of inflorescence, and flower distribution type. Weight of 1.000 seeds and germination rate was according to seed testing method of Vietnam: TCVN 8548:2011.

The data were treated by descriptive statistic Excel software. The value was the mean value (mean \pm standard deviation) of 30 samples. To analyze the correlation of morphological characteristics and seed yield, we used the multiple linear models by SPSS software, version 22 (IPM SPSS statistic Version 22). In which, seed yield was the dependent variable Y; 07 independent variables (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p) were flowering time, inflorescence position, flower distribution, inflorescence length, single flower length, capsules amount per plant, and weight of 1.000 seeds. The linear regression had the form:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2 X_2 + \dots + b_n X_n + \varepsilon \quad \text{Regression coefficient B is not normalized}$$

$$Y = b_1X_1 + b_2 X_2 + \dots + b_n X_n + \varepsilon \quad \text{Regression coefficient B is normalized}$$

Note:

Y: Dependent variable, is variable that affected by another variable.

X, X_1, X_2, X_n : Independent variable, is the variable that affects another variable.

b_0 : Regression constant, also known as the intercept

b_1, b_2, b_n : Regression coefficient, also known as the slope coefficient.

ε : error.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSION

3.1. Agri - Biologies characteristics of some tobacco genetic resources

The results of investigation some agri-biological characteristics of Twenty-four tobacco genetic resources are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Some agri-biological triats of 24 tobacco genetic sources

Variety	Biological height (cm)	Total leaves (leaf/plant)	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf width (cm)	Leaf length/width ratio	Flowering time (day)	Harvesting time (day)
<i>Flue curing tobaccos</i>							
Cocker 411	163.2±7.0	19.4±1.4	60.8±2.9	21.0±2.1	2.9	65.0	101
Cu 263	141.4±8.8	20.6±1.6	56.1±2.8	19.0±1.9	3.0	54.0	94
RG 17	147.4±9.4	21.9±1.3	54.7±4.6	19.9±1.9	2.7	62.0	96
Speight 168	145.9±8.3	20.1±1.5	56.6±3.9	19.7±1.8	2.9	57.0	101
TBE 2	170.4±7.7	15.6±1.0	58.6±5.0	24.8±2.3	2.4	53.0	101
TV 28	192.9±10.2	19.2±1.6	60.6±4.1	22.2±2.1	2.7	53.0	98
TV 30	189.4±10.2	18.2±1.8	57.1±4.6	19.5±1.9	2.9	57.0	96
VT 21	170.5±8.8	22.1±1.6	63.1±2.0	25.6±1.6	2.5	61.0	108
VTL 81	163.3±8.5	24.8±1.8	58.0±3.6	22.7±2.2	2.6	62.0	101
Average	164.9±8.8	20.2±1.5	58.4±3.7	21.6±1.9	2.7	58.2	99.5
<i>Burley tobaccos</i>							
Tennessee 90	178.2±8.8	17.5±1.4	54.1±4.1	28.3±2.6	1.9	57.0	106
Banket A1	168.3±9.6	19.4±1.4	57.5±2.8	27.6±2.6	2.1	64.0	105
Va 528	153.7±7.6	22.5±1.5	53.9±2.8	22.5±1.5	2.4	64.0	100
Kentucky 14	146.9±7.7	21.3±1.1	58.0±2.6	28.7±2.8	2.0	57.0	98
Average	161.8±8.4	20.2±1.4	55.9±3.1	26.7±2.3	2.1	60.5	102.3
<i>Dark tobaccos</i>							
Lào Cai 1	188.5±8.7	17.9±1.4	54.5±3.6	26.6±2.6	2.1	52.0	92
Riogrand	169.8±8.0	19.5±1.6	52.2±2.6	27.8±1.9	1.9	63.0	102
NL Madole	145.6±7.2	11.8±1.1	57.0±4.1	23.6±1.9	2.4	47.0	85
Philip 1	164.7±9.6	20.7±1.0	57.8±2.2	22.7±2.1	2.6	66.0	101
Philip 2	209.2±10.3	16.7±1.4	53.0±3.4	26.1±2.4	2.0	52.0	93
RMB 34	164.1±7.9	20.9±1.0	55.5±3.3	18.7±1.6	3.0	64.0	93
Thang Lay	159.4±7.8	20.8±1.5	53.6±3.2	21.6±1.8	2.5	76.0	110
Nâu QuangNam	177.8±9.3	16.1±1.4	59.8±2.8	25.1±2.1	2.4	61.0	98
Average	172.4±8.6	18.1±1.3	55.4±3.1	24.0±2.1	2.4	60.1	96.8
<i>Cigar tobaccos</i>							
D2	150.6±7.9	16.7±1.6	52.3±3.5	28.2±2.4	1.9	54.0	98
Criocdo	165.7±10.7	16.4±1.5	50.5±2.9	27.2±2.4	1.9	54.0	96
Havana	198.8±11.2	20.0±1.4	56.3±3.8	26.5±1.8	2.1	55.0	96
Average	171±9.9	17.7±1.5	53.1±3.4	27.3±2.2	1.9	54.3	96.7

Biological plant height is an agri-biological factor affecting leaf yield (K. P. Leonova et al., 2020), seed yield and tolerance levels to environmental conditions. According to the data in Table 2, the plant height of the genetic resources ranged from 141.4 to 209.2 cm. There was one tobacco variety with the tallest height, reaching 209.2 cm (Phillip 2); 15 varieties with average height, from 163.2 to 198.8 cm, such as Cocker 411, TV28, Tennessee 90...; and 08 varieties with low height, reaching only 141.4 - 159.4 cm (Cu 263, Rg 17, Kentucky 14...). Some tobacco varieties with too high plant height easily break or fall when meeting unfavourable weather conditions, and taking care of the capsule bunches will be difficult. For tobacco types: Flue-cured tobacco varieties, TV28 and TV30 had the highest height, respectively 192.9 cm and 189.4 cm; then Cocker 411, TBE2, VT 21, and VTL81 (163.2 - 170.4 cm) and other varieties were short height, from 141.4 to 147.4 cm; Burley tobacco varieties, Tennessee 90 had the highest plant height, reaching 178.2 cm,

followed by Banket A1 (168.3 cm) and the lowest is Kentucky 14 (146.9 cm); The Dark tobacco varieties, Philip 2 was the longest stem variety, reaching 209.2 cm and NL Madole was the shortest stem variety (145.6 cm). For Cigar tobacco varieties, the Havana variety had the highest biological plant height, reaching 198.8 cm, and the D2 variety had the low plant height (150.6 cm). With average height, the Flue-cured and Burley tobaccos were the same height, ranging from 161.8 to 164.9 cm, similarly, the average height for Dark and Cigar tobaccos was 171 - 172.4 cm, higher than Flue-curing and Burley tobaccos. Total biological leaves are also an important parameter affecting leaf yield and seed yield, especially fresh yield. The leaves of the varieties ranged from 11.8 to 24.8 leaves/plant. The variety with very few leaves was NL Madole, reaching 11.8 leaves/plant; 07 varieties with few leaves, ranging from 15.6 to 17.9 leaves/plant, including TBE 2, Tennessee 90, NL Madole...; 15 varieties with average total leaves (18.2 - 22.5 leaves/plant) as Cocker 411, Cu 263, Banket A1...; and 01 variety of many leaves was VTL 81, with 24.8 leaves/plant. With tobacco types, the Flue-cured and Burley tobacco varieties had the highest biological leaves, reaching 20.2 ± 1.5 leaves, followed by Dark tobacco varieties (18.1 ± 1.3 leaves), and the lowest in the Cigar varieties (17.7 ± 1.5 leaves).

Leaf length and width are related to leaf area. They are agri-biological factors affecting leaf and seed yield. Because it is related to photosynthetic efficiency and dry matter accumulation in plants. Crops having a suitable leaf size, leaf spacing and closing angle will give a high yield, whereas small leaf size, too narrow/large leaf surface, and closely spaced leaves will be for a low yield. The data in Table 2 showed that the leaf length of the experimental varieties ranged from 50.5 to 63.1 cm. There were 09 varieties with short leaf lengths, from 50.5 to 54.7 cm, such as RG 17, Tennessee 90, and Va 528...; The remaining 15 varieties had average leaf length, ranging from 55.5 to 63.1 cm. For the tobacco types: Flue-cured tobaccos had the long leaf length, reaching 58.4 ± 3.7 cm, followed by Burley and Dark tobaccos: 55.4 - 55.9 cm, and the shortest leaf length belonged to the Cigar tobaccos, with leaf length of 53.1 ± 3.4 cm. Leaf width had an inverse relationship with leaf length. The longer the leaf leads to narrow leaf width, and vice versa. Specifically, the best narrowish leaf width with a size of 21.6 ± 1.9 cm belonged to the group of Flue-cured tobaccos with a long leaf length, while the largest leaf width of 27.3 ± 2.2 cm belonged to the group of Cigars with a short leaf length.

The leaf length/width ratio indicates leaf morphology, which directly affects the fresh yield, the dry yield, as well as the seed yield of each gene source. The leaf length/width ratio of 24 genetic sources in the experiment ranged from 1.9 to 3.0, corresponding to the narrow elliptical to broad elliptical leaf phenotype. The varieties of RMB 34 and Cu 236 had a length/width ratio of 3.0, were small leaf and narrow elliptic leaf phenotype; The broadleaf group as Tennessee 90 (burley), Riogrand (Dark), D2 and Criocdo (cigar) had a length/width ratio of 1.9. The flowering time of the varieties was from 47 to 76 days after planting (DAP). There was 01 very early blooming variety (NL Madole: 47 DAP); 12 early flowering varieties (52 - 57 DAP), 10 medium blooming varieties (58 - 75 DAP), and 01 late blooming variety (Thang Lay: 76 DAP). For the tobacco types, the tobacco groups of Flue-cured, Burley and Dark had an average flowering time, ranging from 58.2 to 60.5 DAP and the Cigar tobaccos were an early blooming (54.3 DAP).

The time from planting to harvesting the capsules of genetic resources was in the range of 85 - 110 days after planting, in which NL Madole had the fastest growth time, with 85 DAP and the latest was Thang Lay, with 110 DAP. The Dark and Cigar tobaccos had earlier capsule harvest time, from 96.7 to 96.8 DAP than the Flue-cured and burley tobaccos (99.5 - 102.3 DAP).

3.2. Some morphological characteristics of the flowers, yield and quality of seeds

Inflorescence position, flower distribution pattern, inflorescence length, the number of capsules/plant and weight of 1.000 seeds are affected by variety traits, which are major agri-biological factors affecting the seed yield of each genetic resource (Leonova, 2020). The experimental results of some biological traits in Table 3.

The inflorescence position determined according to UPOV -2002, is divided into two levels: 1 level: the first blooming bud cluster does not reach higher than the top leaf of the plant; 2 level: a bunch of buds with the first open flower higher than the top leaf of the plant. Based on the above classification, there were 09/24 varieties with low inflorescence positions at the 1 level, including Cigar, Burley, and 2 Dark tobacco varieties (Riogrand and Thang Lay). Other tobacco varieties had a high inflorescence position, at a level of 2. Inflorescence distribution: The shape of the inflorescence depends on the flower density of the main branch, the first and second branches (K. P. Leonova et al., 2020), and is divided into 05 levels: 1: very loose, 3: loose, 5: medium, 7: dense, and 9: very dense (UPOV - 2002). Based on this classification, most of the genetic resources had inflorescence distribution from medium to dense levels (levels: 3 - 7), except the Cigar variety of Criocdo, it had a very loose inflorescence distribution (level: 1). According to the tobacco types, the Flue-cured tobaccos and Burley tobaccos had inflorescences distribution from loose to medium (3 - 5); Dark tobaccos had a more diverse inflorescence distribution, from loose to dense (3 - 7); and Cigar tobaccos had a more-loose inflorescence distribution, from very loose to loose (1 - 3). Specifically, Flue-cured tobacco varieties had 66.6% with medium inflorescence distribution (CU 263, RG 17, TV 30, ..) and 33.3% with loose distribution (Cocker 411, TBE 2, VT). 21,..); Burley varieties: 75% of the cultivars were loose distribution (Tennessee 90, Banket A1 and Kentucky 14) and 25% with medium distribution (Va 528); Dark tobaccos: 50% of varieties were dense distribution (Lao Cai 1, Phillip 2, Thang Lay,..), 25% were medium distribution (Riogrand, RMB 34), and 25% were loose distribution (NL Madole, Phillip 1); Cigar tobaccos: 66.7% varieties were the loose inflorescences distribution (D2 and Havana) and 33.3% of tobacco varieties with very loose inflorescences distribution (Criocdo).

Inflorescence length and width of tobacco varieties ranged from 33.9 to 55.0 cm and 21.2 to 52.9 cm, respectively. The Philip 2 had the largest inflorescence size, with a length of 55.0 cm and a width of 52.9 cm. Among tobacco varieties, the Dark tobacco varieties had the tallest average inflorescence length and width, respectively 46.8 ± 3.6 cm and 37.6 ± 2.8 cm, followed by Flue-cured tobaccos: 43.0 ± 3.1 cm and 33.9 ± 2.6 cm, respectively, and the lowest was Burley tobaccos, reaching 37.2 ± 3.1 cm and 27.9 ± 2.2 cm, respectively. Most varieties had inflorescence length and width proportional to each other. Specifically, the Flue-cured tobacco - TV28, Burley - Kentucky 14, Dark tobacco - Philip 2, and Cigar - Havana had the tallest inflorescence lengths, respectively 52.5 cm, 41.8

cm, 55.0 cm and 38.5 cm, leads to also largest inflorescence width, respectively 41.9 cm, 31.0 cm, 52.9 cm, and 36.0 cm. Meanwhile, varieties that had short inflorescence length were also short inflorescence width. For example, variety of RG17 had a short inflorescence length (38.4 cm), leading to a small inflorescence width, reaching only 29.8 cm. Our research results are consistent with Leonova, 2020, the length and width of inflorescences change according to environmental conditions, but the ratio of inflorescence length/width usually does not change.

The total number of capsules per plant is a major biological factor affecting seed yield, divided into 05 levels: very few (≤ 80 capsules), few (81 - 100 capsules), medium (101 - 120 capsules), many (121 - 140 capsules) and very many (> 140 capsules) (K. P. Leonova et al., 2020). The capsule number of 24 genetic sources varied widely, from very few to very many capsules (69.7 - 295.7 capsules/plant). The varieties of Cocker 411, Cu 263, TBE 2, TV 28, TV 30, VT 21, VT 81, Tennessee 90, Va 528, Kentucky 14, Phillip 1, Philip 2, RMB 34, Quang Nam, D2, Criocdo and Havana belonged to the group of very many capsules, reaching from 143.3 to 295.7 capsules/plant; group of many capsules as Thang Lay (135.7 capsules); group of medium capsules (104.3 - 107.3 capsules) as RG 17, Speight 168, Banket A1, Riogrand; and the group of very few to few capsules (69.7 - 84.7 capsules), including Lao Cai 1 and NL Madole. The average data showed that Cigar tobaccos had the most capsule amounts per plant, with an average of 194.3 ± 8.5 capsules, then the Burley tobaccos: 178 ± 8.9 capsules and the lowest was Flue-cured tobaccos, with 143.3 ± 7.98 capsules.

Individual seed yield depends on biological characteristics, environmental conditions, and the number of capsules per plant. In this study, the weight of seeds/plant varied from 4.3 to 16.8 grams/plant. There were 11 varieties with low seed yield, less than 8 grams/plant, such as Speight 168, RG 17, Cu 263, VTL 81, Riogrand, NL Maldole, Philip 2, Thang Lay, Quang Nam and Lao Cai 1. The remaining varieties had high seed yields, from 8 - 16.8 grams/plant. Except, the Philip 1 variety had the best seed yield, reaching 16.8 grams/plant. Among tobacco types, Burley tobaccos had the highest individual seed yield, an average of 10.8 ± 0.7 grams, followed by Cigar tobaccos of 10.2 ± 0.7 grams, and the lowest is flue-cured tobaccos, reaching 6.2 ± 0.64 grams.

Weight of 1000 seeds of Cocker 411 and D2 varieties reached the highest, from 108.8 - 101.3 mg, followed by TV 28, TV 30, VT 21, VTL 81, Thang Lay, Quang Nam and Criocdo (91.9 - 99.6 mg); the remaining varieties, such as Cu263, RG 17, Speight 168, TBE 2, Tennessee 90, Banket A1, Va 528, Kentucky 14..., only reached 72.9 - 89.9 mg. In tobacco types, the average weight of 1000 seeds of Cigar varieties reached the highest (95.0 ± 7.5 mg), then Flue-cured tobaccos (92.5 ± 7.4 mg); Burley tobaccos (88.3 ± 6.4 mg), and the lowest was Dark tobaccos (83.3 ± 7.1 mg). Percentage germination is one of the most important biological factors in evaluating seed quality. In this study, 24 varieties had germination rates of over 85% after 45 days of harvest, meeting the requirements of basic seed grade according to TCVN 10846:2015. The group of Flue-cured tobaccos had the highest germination rate, reaching 97%, then Cigar tobaccos, with 91%, and the lowest was Burley tobaccos, with a germination rate of 89.8%.

Table 3: Some morphological characteristics of the flowers, yield and seed quality

Variety	Inflorescence position	Inflorescence distribution	Inflorescence length (cm)	Inflorescence width (cm)	individual flower length (cm)	Total capsules/plant (capsule)	Individual seed yield (g)	Theoretical yield (quintals/ha)	Weight of 1000 seeds (mg)	Germination rate (%)
<i>Flue-curing tobacco</i>										
Cocker 411	2	3	42.1±2.8	31.3±2.4	5.51±0.14	182.0±3.6	10.3±1.0	1.43	108.8±7.9	94
Cu 263	2	5	39.1±2.1	33.8±2.6	6.17±0.16	207.7±11.7	6.1±0.3	0.84	88.1±7.5	95
RG 17	2	5	38.4±3.5	29.8±2.4	5.59±0.14	107.3±7.5	5.1±1.0	0.70	85.3±6.6	97
Speight 168	2	5	40.0±3.9	23.1±1.9	5.82±0.16	104.3±6.0	4.3±0.3	0.60	83.8±5.2	93
TBE 2	2	3	44.2±2.9	37.4±2.8	5.71±0.13	165.3±7.2	8.3±0.7	1.15	88.3±7.7	96
TV 28	2	5	52.5±2.8	41.9±2.1	5.60±0.16	211.3±10.3	8.0±0.8	1.11	98.8±8.3	98
TV 30	2	5	47.0±3.5	36.9±3.1	5.37±0.11	151±7.9	13.0±0.9	1.80	96.3±7.4	95
VT 21	2	3	39.9±3.6	36.2±3.4	5.30±0.21	209.3±10.1	10.1±0.5	1.40	96.3±7.4	89
VTL 81	2	5	43.9±3.1	34.6±2.6	6.17±0.17	143.3±7.6	6.2±0.3	0.86	92.5±8.9	97
Average			43.0 ± 3.1	33.9±2.6	6.17±0.15	143.3±7.98	6.2±0.64	0.86	92.5±7.4	97
<i>Burley tobacco</i>										
Tennessee 90	1	3	38.2±3.3	31.1±2.1	5.14±0.14	206.3±10.3	10.4±0.9	1.45	88.8±6.9	91
Banket A1	1	3	33.9±2.8	21.2±2.0	5.25±0.15	112.7±7.5	9.0±0.4	1.25	89.5±6.1	92
Va 528	1	5	35.0±2.5	28.4±2.4	5.12±0.14	153.7±7.8	10.2±0.6	1.42	89.9±6.9	87
Kentucky 14	1	3	41.8±3.6	31.0±2.1	5.13±0.16	239.3±10.1	12.7±1.2	1.76	84.8±5.6	89
Average			37.2±3.1	27.9±2.2	5.16±0.14	178±8.9	10.8±0.7	1.76	88.3±6.4	89.8
<i>Dark tobacco</i>										
Lào Cai 1	2	7	44.8±3.4	32.7±1.8	4.74±0.11	84.7±5.0	6.7±0.2	0.93	74.8±5.7	96
Riogrand	1	5	46.5±3.1	31.2±2.5	5.48±0.16	114.3±4.0	6.6±0.4	0.91	72.9±8.3	89
NL Madole	2	3	40.8±4.1	27.6±2.4	5.37±0.10	69.7±3.2	6.3±0.4	0.87	81.1±7.1	88
Philip 1	2	3	41.4±2.8	35.6±3.3	5.17±0.11	295.7±14.0	16.8±0.9	2.33	82.5±7.1	88
Philip 2	2	7	55.0±5.0	52.9±3.1	4.65±0.12	143.0±8.5	6.7±0.6	0.94	82.8±6.2	94
RMB 34	2	5	51.5±2.8	37.7±3.1	5.26±0.16	231.7±10.4	13.6±1.1	1.89	88.3±7.5	90
Thang Lay	1	7	42.5±3.9	40.6±2.7	5.69±0.12	135.7±6.5	5.8±0.4	0.81	91.9±7.5	86
Nau QuangNam	2	7	51.9±3.3	42.8±2.5	5.47±0.15	233.7±14.8	5.6±0.3	0.78	92.4±7.1	91
Average			46.8±3.6	37.6±2.8	5.2±0.13	153.5±8.3	8.51±0.5	1.2	83.3±7.1	90.3
<i>Cigar tobacco</i>										
D2	1	3	38.2±3.1	31.1±2.1	5.14±0.13	259.7±10.6	9.8±0.6	1.37	101.3±8.3	86
Criocdo	1	1	35.7±3.5	33.5±2.0	5.58±0.12	168.3±7.6	10.9±1.0	1.51	99.6±7.6	93
Havana	1	3	38.5±2.9	36.0±3.1	5.11±0.10	155.0±7.2	10.0±0.7	1.38	84.1±6.5	94
Average			37.5±3.2	33.5±2.4	5.3±0.1	194.3±8.5	10.2±0.7	1.42	95.0±7.5	91.0

3.3. Correlation analysis between some biological factors of flowers and seed yield

To determine the relationship between biological factors of inflorescence, flower and seed yield, we selected the main characteristics affecting seed yield based on published literature and practical experience in tobacco seed production. According to a study by Leonova, 2020, the flower density, number of flowers per plant, seed weight/plant, seed weight/ha, inflorescence length and width, and weight of 1.000 seeds were the main agri-biological traits affecting the seed yield. In processing production, we have realized that the characteristics of flowering time, inflorescence position, flower length, and number of capsules per plant can affect the seed yield. To evaluate their effect on seed yield/plant through multiple linear regression analysis, we selected the 07 main agri-biological traits related to tobacco seed yield.

In this model, seed yield is the dependent variable, and 07 other characteristics, such as flowering time, inflorescence position, Inflorescence distribution, inflorescence length, and Flower length, number of capsules and weight of 1000 seeds are independent variables. The results of analysis agri-biological traits according to IPM SPSS statistic Version 22 are at Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7.

Table 4: Agri-biological traits of inflorescence and flower in multiple linear regression analysis with seed yield

No	Characteristic	Medium	Min	Max
1	Flowering time (day)	58.8	47.0	76.0
2	Inflorescence position	1.6	1.0	2.0
3	Inflorescence distribution	3.6	1.0	7.0
4	Inflorescence length (cm)	42.6	33.9	55.0
5	Single flower length (cm)	5.40	4.65	6.17
6	Capsules/plan (Capsule)	170.2	69.7	295.7
7	Weight of 1.000 seeds (mg)	89.3	72.9	108.8
8	Seed weight/plant (g)	8.8	4.3	16.8

Table 5: Analysis of Variance ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	189.535	7	27.076	13.030	.000 ^b
	Residual	33.248	16	2.078		
	Total	222.783	23			

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Yield; b. Predictors: (Constant), 50% Flowing time, inflorescence length, Weight of 1.000 seeds, Fflower length, Capsules/plan, Inflorescence position, Inflorescence distribution

The ANOVA analysis results in Table 5 showed that value Sig = 0.000 (< 0.05), which proved that the using multiple linear regression model was appropriate. The correlation coefficient R (Table 6) reached 0.922, demonstrating a close relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The coefficients of determination R² (R Square) and adjusted R² (Adjusted R Square) were both high, reaching 0.851 and 0.785, respectively, so 07 biological characteristics of flowers influenced 78.5% of the seed yield; The remaining 21.5% were due to out of model variables and random error. Durbin - Watson value = 2,170, in the range of 1.5 - 2.5, once again confirming the suitability of

the model used to evaluate the correlation between agri-biological characteristics of flowers and seed yield.

Table 6: Summary of regression model^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.922 ^a	.851	.785	1.44153232322414	2.170

Note: a. Predictors: (Constant), 50% flowering time, inflorescence length, Weight of 1.000 seeds, Single flower length, Capsules/plant, Inflorescence position, Inflorescence distribution; b. Dependent Variable: yield

The regression coefficients and the impact of each trait on productivity are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	21.170	6.266		3.379	.004	
	Weight of 1.000 seeds	-.007	.042	-.019	-.173	.865	.736
	Capsules	.020	.006	.366	3.099	.007	.667
	inflorescence length	.059	.076	.108	.779	.447	.486
	Single flower length	-4.244	.938	-.504	-4.527	.000	.754
	Inflorescence distribution	-1.228	.228	-.695	-5.384	.000	.560
	Inflorescence position	.795	.781	.126	1.018	.324	.606
	50% flowering time	.157	.054	.318	2.909	.010	.783

a. Dependent Variable: yield

The characteristics of capsules/plant, off flowering time, Inflorescence distribution and flower length all had Sig values (P-value) < 0.05, so they were statistically significant; Variance magnification factor (VIF) < 2, this can be confirmed that 04 characteristics had a direct impact on seed yield/plant. The remaining characteristics did not directly impact seed weight / plant (Sig > 0.05). So seed yield positively correlated with the number of capsules per plant, time of flowering and negatively correlated with flower length and inflorescence distribution.

Based on the main agri-biological factors affecting individual seed yield, the normalized (1) and unnormalized (2) multivariable regression equations were as follows:

$$(1) \text{ Yield} = -0.695 * \text{Inflorescence distribution} - 0.504 * \text{Flower length} + 0.366 * \text{Capsules} + 0.318 * \text{flowering time} + \epsilon$$

$$(2) \text{ Yield} = 21.17 - 4.244 * \text{Flower length} - 1.228 * \text{Inflorescence distribution} + 0.157 * \text{flowering time} + 0.020 * \text{Capsules} + \epsilon$$

Fig 1: Normalized residual frequency plot of Histogram

Evaluation of regression assumptions through histogram normalized residual frequency (Figure 1) showed mean (Mean) = $-1.28E-15$ (asymptote to 0), standard deviation of 0.834, and price columns the residual value. The residual value was bell-shaped, so it concluded that the residual distribution was approximately normal, and assuming the normal distribution of the residuals was not violated, it could ensure the correct model in the correlation analysis between agri-biological characteristics of flowers and tobacco seed yield.

DISCUSSION

Through initial research results, the topic determined the biological height of the plant affected the seed yield of tobacco plants and was consistent with the research results of K. P. Leonova et al., 2020. Height plants that were too low/too high reduced seed yield. The low biological plant height reduced seed yield more strongly than too high. For example, the Flue-cured tobaccos had a short plant height, from 141.4 - 147.4 cm leading to the lowest seed yield, only 4.3 - 6.1 grams/plant; the plant height from 163.2 - 189.4 cm was the highest seed yield (from 6.2 - 13 grams/plant); When the plant height was too tall, above 192.9 cm, the seed yield tended to decrease, reaching only 08 grams/plant. Cigar tobaccos: D2 variety had a short length (150.6 cm), the seed yield was 9.8 grams/plant; Plant height of 165.7 cm, the seed yield was 10.9 grams/plant; and above 198.8 cm, seed yield of plant decreased slightly (10 grams/plant). Dark tobaccos: Low plant height, from 145.6 - 159.4 cm, seed yield was 5.8 - 6.3 grams; from 164.1 - 164.7 cm, seed yield was 13.6 - 16.8 grams; and over 169.8 cm, seed yield tended to decrease slightly (5.6 - 6.7 grams). Except, the Burley tobaccos, the seed yield was less affected by biological height. When the plant height was too high or too low, it reduced the photosynthetic area of the plant leading to a decreasing in dry matter accumulation and affecting the development of flowers and capsules. Due to the short height varieties, the

leaves are closely spaced/the high plants shade many of the lower leaves leading to decreasing in the photosynthetic quality of the leaves.

According to studies by foreign authors, the phenotypic characteristics of the varieties had a weak influence on the 50% flowering time, the seed yield of the plant and the seed yield per capsule (Y. BHARATHI et al., 2018), and consistent with the research results of the phenotypes of the studied gene sources. The phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) because the phenotype depended on genotype and environmental conditions (Y. BHARATHI) et al., 2018). GCV determined up to 11.92% of 50% flowering time and 34.56% of individual seed yield. The genotypic coefficient of variation strongly affected the seed yield of the plant and each capsule. Genotypic was used the genotype coefficient for the phenotype in the breeding materials. Flowering days, plant height, and capsule weight are closely related to the genotype heritability coefficient. This information will help breeders have a basis for phenotypic selection because of the high heritability for morphological traits. The heritability of expression was high with capsule weight per plant, then seed yield/plant and seed yield per capsule (Y. BHARATHI et al., 2018). Evaluation of heritability by gene determined the best performance of selected individuals (Johnson et al., 1955a). According to Panse, 1957, capsule weight and seed yield of plants were highly heritable with genotype; Comstock et al., 1949: the capsule quantity, plant height and the days of flowering 50% were high heritable. The coefficient of genetic variation had a low effect on the 50% flowering time of plants. Seed yield per plant was statistically highly significant and positively related to capsule weight/plant and single capsule in both phenotypic and genotypic thresholds, while negatively correlated with 50% flowering time and plant height. The number of capsules/plant, the weight of each capsule, and the seed yield were statistically significant and strongly correlated (Y. BHARATHI et al., 2018). According to Y. BHARATHI et al., 2018, the weight of the capsules per plant was strongly and positively related to the seed yield of each plant. 50% flowering days had little or no negative impact on seed yield. Plant height had a positive effect on seed yield, but some other characteristics had a negative impact on the seed yield. In addition, the fertilizer factor also affected the seed yield. Increasing nitrogen above 90N also significantly increased the seed yield (Yingchao Lin et al., 2020). The total capsule number of the plant was closely related to seed yield but had little effect on the weight of 1000 seeds and germination rate. Tobacco plant have many capsules leads to increasing the seed yield/plant. For example, Burley and Cigar tobacco varieties had a total number of 198 - 194.3 capsules/plant leads to having the highest seed yield, from 10.2 - 10.8 grams; Followed by Dark tobaccos have total number of 153.5 capsules, the seed yield only reached 8.51 grams, Flue-cured tobaccos had the least total number of capsules, only 143.3 capsules/plant leading to the low seed yield, reaching 6.2 grams. Through the results of statistical analysis, the number of capsules/plant, the time of flower development, the distribution of flowers and the length of single flowers all affected the seed yield, with Sig value < 0.05 and the coefficient of variance exaggeration (VIF) < 2, in which, seed yield had a positive correlation with capsules per plant and maturation time, and had a negative correlation with flower length and flower distribution.

4. CONCLUSION

In the experimental genetic resources, Dark and cigar tobacco varieties had the highest biological height (171 - 172.4 cm), then Flue-curing tobaccos (164.9 cm), and the lowest was Burley tobaccos. Tobacco varieties had total leaves from 17.7 - 20.2 leaves/plant. The highest leaves number belonged to the Flue-curing and Burley tobaccos (20.2 leaves/plant), and the least was the Cigar varieties (17.7 leaves/plant). The Flue-curing tobaccos had the tallest leaf length but the best narrow leaf width, respectively 58.4 cm and 21.6 cm; For the Cigar tobaccos, the leaf length was short (53.1 cm), but the leaf width was largest (27.3 cm). The weight of 1000 seeds and the germination rate of the genetic resources met the quality requirements according to the standard of Vietnam.

Initially determined the flower distribution, single flower length, number of capsules/plant and sexual development time affected 78.5% of seed yield/plant. Seed yield was positively correlated with the number of capsules/plants and maturation time but negatively correlated with flower length and inflorescence distribution. Experimental results were important information for breeding, seed production and selection of genotypes which were beneficial for tobacco material production and research.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- 1) Andrade, D.B., Silva, H.P., Carvalho, M.L.M., Oliveira, A.S., Santos, H.O., Silva Neta, I.C. (2018). Morphological, physiological, and biochemical indicators of quality in tobacco fruits and seeds. *Genetics and Molecular Research*, 17 (4) gmr18058. DOI: 10.4238/gmr18058.
- 2) Sebahattin Albayrak and Özgür TÖNGEL. (2012). Path analysis of yield and yield-related traits of common vetch (*Vicia sativa* L.) under different rainfall conditions. *OMU Zir. Fak. Dergisi*, 2006,21(1):27-32/*J. of Fac. of Agric., OMU*, 2006,21(1):27-32
- 3) Y. Bharathi, S. Jaffarbasha and J. Manjunath. (2018). Variability, Correlation and Path Analysis for Seed Yield and Its Component Traits in Bidi Tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* L). *The J. Res. PJTSAU* 46(2&3) 99-102, 2018.
- 4) Nguyen Van Chin, Nguyen Van Van, and Pham Ha Thanh. (2023). the technical process of using biological and chemical pesticides to control insects and viral diseases damaging the tobacco plants in Vietnam. *Adv. Biores.* Vol 14 [1] March 2023; 133-142.
- 5) Comstock, R.E., H.F. Robinson and P.H. Harvey. (1949). A breeding procedure designed to make maximum use of both general and specific combining ability. *Agronomy Journal*. 41: 360-367.
- 6) Darvishzadeh R, Alavi SR, Sarafi A. (2011): Genetic variability for chlorine concentration in oriental tobacco genotypes. *Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science*, 57, 167–177.
- 7) FAO. (2014). *Genebank Standards for Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture*. Rev. ed. Rome
- 8) Tran Thi Thanh Hao. (2022). Conservation of tobacco genetic resources. Report of Tobacco Research Institute, Vietnam National Tobacco Corporation.

- 9) Johnson, H.W., H.F. Robinson and R.E. Comstock. (1955a). Estimation of genetic and environmental variability in soybean. *Agronomy Journal*. 47: 314-318.
- 10) Khomutova, S.A., Salomatin, V.A., Kubakhova, A.A. (2015). Use of genetic resources of the world tobacco collection for breeding. *Scientific journal KubSAU*, 110 (06), 1–11 (in Russian).
- 11) Kovtunyk, I.M., Goncharuk, V.Ya., Stelmashchuk, A.M., Pashchenko, I.M., Dadiani, R.G., Byalkovska, H.D. (2001). Tobacco. Growing, processing. Kamianets-Podolsky: Abetka (in Ukrainian).
- 12) Lázaro A. Maqueira-López, Rogelio Morejón-Rivera, Osmany Roján-Herrera, Walfredo Torres-de-la-Noval. (2019). Relationship between growth traits and yield formation in Indica-type rice crop. *Agron. Mesoam*. 230(1):79-100. Enero-abril, 2019. Doi: 10.15517/ma. v30i1.29671.
- 13) Yingchao Lin, Dejun Kong, Zhihong Wang, Yi Chen, Zhixiao Yang, Chun Wu, Hui Yang, and Lili Chen. (2020). Nitrogen Application Modifies the Seed and Oil Yields and Fatty Acid Composition of *Nicotiana tabacum*. *HORTSCIENCE* 55(12):1898–1902. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTSCI115335-20>.
- 14) Leonova, K.P., Morgun, A.V., Hospodarenko, H.M., Ketskalo, V.V., Kotsyuba, S.P., Nevlad, V.I. (2020). Evaluation of the tobacco genotypes by seed productivity. *Ukrainian Journal of Ecology*, 10(2), 449-454.
- 15) Moon, H.S. J.S. Nicholson. A. Heineman. K. Lion. R. van der Hoeven. A.J. Hayes. and R.S. Lewis. (2009). Changes in genetic diversity of U.S. flue-cured tobacco germplasm over seven decades of cultivar development. *Crop Sci*. 49:498–508.
- 16) Panse V.G. 1957. Genetics of quantitative characters in Relation to plant breeding. *Indian journal of Genetics*. 17: 318-28.
- 17) Z. Porkabiri, N. Sabaghnia, R. Ranjbar, h.h. maleki. (2028). Genetic variation of some tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) genotype by morphological traits. *Plant Sciences. Scientia agriculturae bohemica*, 50, 2019 (1): 1–7.
- 18) Ren N, Timko MP. (2001). AFLP analysis of genetic polymorphism and evolutionary relationships among cultivated and wild *Nicotiana* species. *Genome*, 44, 559–571.
- 19) Savina, O.I., Matiega, O.O., Kovalyuk, O.M. (2007). Aspects of tobacco breeding for the formation of high seed productivity. *Problems of the Agrarian Complex of the Carpathians*, 16, 116–120.
- 20) Savina, O.I., Kovalyuk, O.M., Sheidyk, K.A. (2017). Optimization of the variety model to increase seed productivity. *Variety research and protection of plant variety rights*, 13 (1), 34–42.
- 21) UPOV. (2022). Guidelines for the conduct of tests for distinctness, uniformity and stability. TG/195/1. Tobacco, 2022-04-17. <http://www.upov.int/en/publications/tg-rom/tg195/tg-195-1.pdf>.
- 22) Wenping LI, Zhu L, Zhao S. (2009). Correlation and path coefficient analysis and Euclidean distance clustering for several characters in tobacco germplasm resource. *Chinese Tobacco Science*, 30, 59–63.
- 23) Zeba N, Isbat M. (2011). Multivariate analysis for yield and yield contributing traits in F0 and F1 generations in tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*). *Journal of Experimental Bioscience*, 2, 101-106.